

Performance of 316 L and 304 L stainless steels in the APBS-CDRMax[®] solvent for CO₂ capture processes: Insights into corrosion resistance and stability

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on investigating the corrosion performance of SS 304 L and SS 316 L stainless steels when exposed to the APBS-CDRMax[®] solvent, under various conditions, including CO₂ and presence of SO_x/NO_x contaminants. Electrochemical techniques, including potentiodynamic and cyclic polarization are employed, along with Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) analysis to evaluate both the short-term corrosion rate and the pitting tendency. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) coupled with Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) analysis provide insights into the underlying corrosion mechanism. Long term exposure tests are also carried out at temperatures up to 90°C to assess the long-term corrosion behavior of the stainless steels and stability of the solvent. Findings indicate that APBS-CDRMax[®] presents extremely low corrosion rates, even in the presence of high concentrations of sulfuric and nitric acid used to simulate the effects of SO_x and NO_x dissolution. The observed corrosion rates are multiple times lower than those of the benchmark monoethanolamine (MEA) solvent. Microscopic observation and EDX analysis identify the presence of black layers associated with amine byproducts and different types of corrosion precipitates, many of which are linked to the inherent properties of the solvent. Long-term exposure tests indicate a tendency for the stainless steels to form corrosion precipitates, confirming the solvent's exceptional low corrosivity over time and reveal a stabilization of the corrosion process after 7–10 days of exposure to the solvent. Following extended exposure of the solvent to conditions causing thermal degradation, only minor signs of degradation are observed. The solvent's CO₂ loading capacity remains virtually unaffected, whereas both density and viscosity remain stable.

1. Introduction

Post-combustion capture (PCC) is recognized as an indispensable approach for fulfilling the Net Zero industry targets [1], as despite the contributions of (renewable) electrification, extensive hard-to-abate emitters will continue to exist. PCC with amine-based chemical absorption is currently a mature technology for short-term, industrial implementation [2]. However, on the road to wide deployment, amine-based systems need to overcome a number of challenges including equipment corrosion that leads to decreased plant operational efficiency, high maintenance costs, and even safety issues [3,4]. As

carbon steel and other steel alloys serve as main plant construction materials, localized and pitting corrosion are reported as the most frequent causes of material failure [5]. While the overall corrosion rate may be affected by the plant's location (i.e., external climatic conditions), typically, causal factors for corrosion-based failures are primarily internal, and related to the type of solvent (molecular structure, tendency to degrade) and range of operating conditions (temperature, pressure, presence of impurities in the flue gas) [4,6].

Aqueous amine solutions after reacting with acid gases, like CO₂ can generate oxidizing agents, increase solution conductivity, and lower pH. These factors collectively accelerate material corrosion [7]. Components

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such as O₂, SO_x, and NO_x in flue gas, extensive flashing and elevated operating temperatures in the regeneration section contribute to solvent degradation and to the formation of degradation byproducts, exacerbating corrosion [8]. Such factors contribute to establishing a self-sustained process as degradation routes are understood to be catalyzed by metal cations leaching due to equipment corrosion [9].

Given the propensity of amines to induce corrosion, preventative measures have been researched, including operational optimizations and corrosion management strategies [10–12]. Nevertheless, there is still no solvent scoring high on all relative selection indices [13]. For example, in its early stages of development PCC has used aqueous monoethanolamine (MEA) as benchmark solvent [14,15]. However, MEA presents significant limitations, one of the most prominent being the very high corrosion tendency of its CO₂-loaded solutions, which limits its operating concentrations to 30 wt% in packed bed capture processes [4,16,17].

Such issues have driven the development of alternative solvents [14]. The strategy of amine blending has resulted in mixtures of improved performance [18,19]. Notably, Carbon Clean has developed an innovative solvent containing amine-promoted buffer salts, known as APBS-CDRMax®, as an alternative to MEA. This solvent represents a significant advancement, as it combines high CO₂ absorption rates, substantial CO₂ capacity, low regeneration energy requirements, and reduced corrosion rates, among other benefits [20]. The upscaling of this proprietary solvent is currently pursued through a number of research projects, pilot plants and commercial projects aimed at large-scale deployment worldwide [21–23].

Carbon steel is widely used in CO₂ capture units due to its low cost, mechanical strength, and availability [24,25], but its susceptibility to corrosion limits long-term performance [26]. Stainless steel has therefore attracted attention as an alternative for process equipment because of its superior corrosion resistance [26]. Among stainless steels, 304 L and 316 L are preferred for their excellent corrosion resistance, ductility, toughness, and ease of fabrication.

Up to date, only few studies have examined the corrosion behavior of APBS-CDRMax® solutions using ICP analysis [16,27]. Nonetheless, this study introduces, for the first time, an extensive and comprehensive analysis of APBS-CDRMax® amine corrosion behavior using high-precision electrochemical methods. These methods enable quantitative assessment of the solvent's corrosivity.

This study investigates the corrosion behavior of two stainless steels, 316 L and 304 L, in APBS-CDRMax® solvents, using an extensive combination of electrochemical techniques providing key insights into corrosion parameters such as current, potential, and rate, enhancing the understanding of the underlying corrosion mechanisms. Employing scanning electron microscopy, the microstructural features of the corroded samples are examined, and a more detailed analysis of surface degradation is performed. This study further analyzes the solvent to identify properties that may influence corrosion behavior. In particular, the stability of APBS-CDRMax® under prolonged thermal degradation conditions (ageing) is investigated, by monitoring changes in its physical properties, and the consequent impact of the degraded solvent on corrosion behavior is evaluated. Through long term exposure tests at low (25 °C) and high temperatures (90 °C) the impact of prolonged contact of metallic samples with the corrosive and degraded solutions is assessed. The solvent is studied under various conditions, including i) lean or CO₂-loaded, ii) fresh or aged, iii) pure or mixed with sulfuric (H₂SO₄) and nitric acid (HNO₃) to simulate the absorption of SO_x and NO_x, common contaminants in the process flue gas of post-combustion CO₂ capture (PCC) plants. Results obtained from electrochemical measurements are compared with those of MEA, that can be found in a previously published work [28]. The comparison provides a clearer perspective on the significantly improved corrosion performance offered by APBS-CDRMax®.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and Metal sample preparation

APBS-CDRMax® solvent batches were used as received (supplied by Carbon Clean) without further purification. MEA (Merck, purity 99 %, used as received) solutions were prepared by diluting with deionized water. Gaseous CO₂ (BUSE, purity 99.995 %) was used for loading the solvent. Contaminants were added in the form of liquid sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄, Fischer chemicals, purity ≥95 %) and nitric acid (HNO₃, Thermo Scientific, 70 % pure in water) to simulate the effect of SO₂ and NO/NO₂ dissolution in the solvent.

Electrochemical corrosion and long-term exposure experiments were carried out using rod-shaped samples of 304 L and 316 L stainless steel, each measuring 6 mm in diameter and 5 mm in height. Prior to each electrochemical test, the samples underwent meticulous preparation through wet grinding. This procedure involved sequentially using silicon carbide grinding papers with grit sizes of P800, P1000, and P1200, ensuring uniform polishing of both the flat surfaces and the perimeter. After grinding, the specimens were thoroughly rinsed with deionized water and ethanol, then dried using hot air.

The microstructure of these materials is presented in Fig. 1, while the chemical composition is provided in Table 1.

Both stainless steels exhibit a fully austenitic microstructure characterized by fine, equiaxed grains with clearly defined boundaries. Numerous intragranular and grain-boundary precipitates are dispersed throughout the matrix; these appear as dark, roughly spherical or irregular particles. Deformation twins are also evident within many grains, appearing as straight, parallel lamellae indicative of prior cold-working or mechanical deformation. While the general microstructural features of the two alloys are similar, SS 316 L contains a higher density of precipitates, consistent with its slightly different alloying chemistry. Overall, both microstructures are typical of wrought, low-carbon austenitic stainless steels.

In the case of thermal degradation experiments, stainless steel 316 L hollow cylindrical specimens (length 2 cm, O.D. 1.27 cm, wall thickness 0.0889 cm) were immersed in the liquid solvent to study the course of metal ion leaching throughout the prolonged experiments of thermal degradation.

3. Methods

3.1. Electrochemical corrosion experiments

The electrochemical corrosion experiments were performed using a three-electrode electrochemical cell. The reference electrode was an Ag/AgCl electrode (saturated KCl), while a platinum rod served as the counter electrode. The working electrode consisted of either 304 L or 316 L stainless steel. The electrochemical cell was connected to the Gamry Instruments Interface 1010E Potentiostat for precise control and measurement. Data analysis was conducted using the Echem Analyst software, ensuring accurate interpretation of the results. All the tests were conducted at room temperature (25 °C), under atmospheric pressure.

The experimental procedure began with the submersion of the samples in each tested solution, followed by the measurement of the Open Circuit Potential (OCP). Once the OCP stabilized, electrochemical tests were conducted. For all solutions examined and for both steels, the OCP value reached a steady state within 30 min of immersion. For polarization experiments, a scan rate of 2 mV/s was applied, with the potential range set from –800 mV to +900 mV (versus SCE) relative to the SCE. During cyclic polarization, the reverse scan concluded at –800 mV (versus SCE). Each electrochemical experiment was repeated a minimum of three times to ensure the reliability and consistency of the results. Additionally, all extracted curves were normalized to the same surface area to facilitate accurate comparisons. The surface area of the

Fig. 1. Microstructure of: [a] SS 304 L and [b] SS 316 L from optical microscope.

Table 1

Chemical composition of SS 316 L and SS 304 L samples used in the experimental procedure.

%	C	Cr	Mn	Si	P	Ni	S	Mo	Fe
SS 304 L	0.03	18	2	1	0.0045	8	0.03	-	Bal.
SS 316 L	0.022	17.5	1.8	-	0.003	10	0.54	2	Bal.

working electrodes used for polarization measurements was 1.2 cm².

3.2. Long term exposure experiments

For the long-term exposure experiments, stainless steel specimens were placed in sealed 100 ml containers filled with various APBS-CDRMax® amine solutions. The experiments were performed in accordance with ASTM G31 – 72, which provides standardized guidelines for static immersion testing to evaluate mass loss. The experiments were conducted at both 25 °C and 90 °C, using a Climacell temperature-controlled furnace (Climacell 222, MMM Group). After 3, 5, 7, 12 and 24 days, coupons were removed, cleaned in a water bath, dried and then weighed using a precision balance with four-digit accuracy (0.1 mg resolution) to determine their final mass. In long term exposure tests, the weight loss percentage is determined by the difference between the initial and final masses, dividing that by the initial mass and then multiplying by 100% (Eq. 1).

$$\text{weight loss(\%)} = \left[\frac{m_{\text{initial}} - m_{\text{final}}}{m_{\text{initial}}} \right] \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

The temperatures of 25 °C and 90 °C were selected to represent typical process conditions in industrial amine-based CO₂ capture units. Absorption generally occurs at moderate temperatures, approximately 20–80 °C, while solvent regeneration (stripping) is carried out at higher temperatures, typically in the range of 80–120 °C. These values were chosen to provide a realistic representation of both low- and high-temperature operational conditions.

3.3. Solvent ageing protocol – thermal degradation experiments

APBS-CDRMax® and MEA 30 wt% batches (200 g) were prepared and introduced into borosilicate glass containers of 500 ml volume. The hollow cylindrical SS 316 L specimen was immersed in the solvent and the container was sealed. Specifically, i) Series “contaminated” (CONT in sample annotation) included a set of three containers with CO₂-unloaded APBS-CDRMax® and MEA 30 wt% mixed with 1.9 wt% H₂SO₄ and 1.2 wt% HNO₃, ii) Series “contaminated and loaded” (CONT-L in sample annotation) included a set of three containers of APBS-CDRMax® and MEA 30 wt% mixed with 1.9 wt% H₂SO₄ and 1.2 wt% HNO₃ and loaded with CO₂.

In series CONT and CONT-L acidic contaminants were added at a total concentration of 3.1 wt% to represent an extreme case of heavy contamination that may occur as contaminants would accumulate in the solvent after prolonged use in a pilot plant. In the case of CONT-L series the loading with CO₂ was performed after the acid mixing and took place in a dedicated experimental apparatus described in Tzirakis et al. [29]. For the CO₂ loading procedure, a CO₂ gas stream was bubbled in the solvent for a pre-estimated time duration targeting a CO₂ content around 1.90 – 2.1 mol CO₂/kg solvent. The CO₂ gas stream flowed through a series of gas wash bottles immersed in a temperature-controlled water bath. The first gas wash bottle contained de-ionized water acting as a humidifier. The second gas wash bottle contained the solvent. The third gas wash bottle was used as a trap for potential droplets possibly drifting with the gas stream and the fourth gas wash bottle was maintained at lower temperature as a condensation trap for volatile amines.

According to the solvent ageing protocol three containers of each solvent were placed inside the temperature-controlled furnace (Climacell) to be kept at 90 °C for a period of up to 30 days (720 h). One container of each series was removed periodically, after 10, 20 and 30 days (240, 480 and 720 h respectively). After removing the container, the liquid solvent was analyzed for amine concentration (with acid – base titrations), density (with a Gay-Lussac pycnometer), viscosity (with an Anton Paar, Visco-QC300-L rotational viscometer, B-DG26 measuring bob and C-DG26/SS measuring cup), and accumulation of metals iron (Fe), nickel (Ni), chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn) and molybdenum (Mo) (with a Perkin Elmer, model ICP-OES 4300 DV). The hollow cylindrical sample was weighed to assess weight loss and was then subjected to SEM microscopy.

Acid-base titrations were performed with 0.5 M HCl_(aq) and 0.1 M NaOH_(aq) for each sample of MEA and APBS-CDRMax® ultimately leading to the calculation of a degradation rate, as proposed by Lepaumier et al. [30] based on Eq. (2).

$$\Psi = \frac{C_i}{C_0} \times 100; \text{amine loss} = 100 - \Psi \quad (2)$$

where Ψ is the degradation rate, C is the remaining amine concentration after i days of ageing and C_0 is the initial amine concentration in the fresh solvent.

Viscosity, η , was measured at 40 ± 0.05 °C and 60 ± 0.05 °C by pouring 7.5 ml of a solvent sample inside the measuring cup. The measurement is set at “stop at time” mode with a duration of 5 min. The results are presented in the form of an average value in [mPa s] units and the standard deviation is reported as the percentage error.

Density, ρ , of solvent samples was measured with a 10 ml Gay-Lussac pycnometer and a precision scale at room temperature (25 °C). According to the measuring methodology, the weight of the empty pycnometer and the pycnometer filled with deionized water are recorded. The two values are subtracted to calculate the net weight of water and to calculate its density at the given temperature. Then, the weight of the

pycnometer filled with the solvent is recorded. The sample's density is calculated via Eq. (3).

$$\rho_{\text{solvent sample}} = \frac{W_{\text{solvent sample}}}{W_{\text{water}}} \times \rho_{\text{water at the given temperature}} \quad (3)$$

A schematic representation of the experimental procedure employed for the thermal degradation experiments is presented in Fig. 2 to facilitate a clearer understanding of the overall process.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Potentiodynamic polarization curves

Fig. 3 illustrates typical potentiodynamic polarization curves obtained from SS 304 L and 316 L samples immersed in various APBS-CDRMax® solutions, either lean or loaded with CO₂, at the temperature of 25 °C. Table 2 presents the electrochemical values determined by the Tafel extrapolation method. Standard deviations were calculated for all electrochemical measurements to assess the reproducibility of the corrosion-rate data. The deviations were found to be very small: the maximum variation in i_{corr} across all steels and solutions was $\pm 0.003 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, corresponding to a maximum deviation of $\pm 0.26 \mu\text{mpy}$ in the calculated corrosion rates.

As depicted in the polarization curves of SS 304 L and SS 316 L in Fig. 3(a, b), the anodic curves for each solution can be divided into distinct regions corresponding to the reactions occurring at the metal surface. In stage I, an active corrosion region is evident across all curves, indicative of metal dissolution. This is followed by stage II, characterized by a noticeable decrease in the slope of the anodic curves, reflecting a slower rise in current density relative to the applied potential. This behavior signifies a reduction in the metal dissolution rate, likely due to the formation and precipitation of corrosion products on the metal surface, which limits the availability of active anodic sites. Notably, stage II spans a broad potential range, suggesting that the APBS-CDRMax® solvent samples promote favorable conditions for the deposition of corrosion byproducts under all examined conditions. However, these depositions may be too thin, non-uniform or unstable to provide effective protection to the underlying material. Furthermore, in SS 304 L, the current densities during stage II remain similar across all solutions, indicating that even the introduction of SO_x/NO_x and CO₂ does not affect the protectiveness of the passive layer. In contrast, for SS 316 L, the stage II in solutions with contaminants is associated with lower current densities, suggesting that the passive layers formed in these conditions are considered more protective. Finally, a sharp increase in current density is observed at higher potentials (stage III), corresponding either to the evolution of oxygen or the breakdown of the passive film and the onset of localized corrosion [31]. An exception is observed for SS 304 L immersed in unloaded APBS-CDRMax® solution. In this case, two distinct passive regions are present, with the first one

being very steep (from -700 mV to -600 mV) while the second one extends from -200 mV to 600 mV . The first passive region is followed by an abrupt increase in current density, possibly indicating a pitting tendency at such low potential values.

Also, as presented in Table 2, the corrosion potential of the SS 316 L curves is slightly more positive than that of SS 304 L, offering a preliminary indication of SS 316 L's superior corrosion resistance across all tested solutions. Generally, it is evident that the E_{corr} values are remarkably low in all the examined solutions, for both stainless steels, compared to the corresponding MEA-based solutions [28]. This may be attributed to the inherent properties of this novel amine solution. The variations observed among the tested APBS-CDRMax® solutions may arise from slight differences in solution composition, such as the presence of CO₂ loading or dissolved contaminants, but overall, the corrosion potentials remain lower than those typically reported for MEA systems.

Notably, the cathodic segments of the polarization curves for both stainless steels exhibit a very shallow slope across all examined solutions, indicating that cathodic reactions occur at a significantly fast rate. This behavior is likely due to the efficient reduction of oxidizing species present in the solutions. The high cathodic activity may also explain the extended potential range observed in stage II of the anodic curves. Overall, the passivation process is inherently complex, as it must compete with active metal dissolution. For passivation to occur, the formation of a protective layer must outpace the metal dissolution process. This condition is met only when a strong cathodic reaction supports passivation [32]. In the case of APBS-CDRMax®, the presence of sufficient cathodic reactions facilitates the formation of passivation layers, effectively slowing down the corrosion process.

Fig. 4 shows comparably the corrosion rates for SS 304 L and SS 316 L at 25 °C, when immersed in APBS-CDRMax® and in the benchmark MEA solution. The corrosion rates for APBS-CDRMax® are calculated from the Tafel extrapolation method of Fig. 3, while the corrosion rates for the MEA solutions have been calculated in our previously published study [28].

As shown in Fig. 4, the corrosion rates for both stainless steels are consistently lower (multiple times) in APBS-CDRMax® compared to MEA across all examined conditions. This highlights the superior corrosion resistance of APBS-CDRMax®. Notably, in scenarios involving the presence of SO_x and NO_x contaminants, whether under CO₂-loaded or unloaded conditions, the corrosion rate in MEA shows a significant increase. In contrast, APBS-CDRMax® exhibits only a slight increase in corrosion rate, indicating that the presence of these impurities has little impact on the overall corrosion process. This observation highlights the enhanced corrosion resistance of APBS-CDRMax®, even in the presence of such high concentrations of acidic contaminants.

Generally, various reactions can occur in a system containing amine solvent, CO₂ and SO_x NO_x impurities, all of which can significantly affect the corrosion process. The reaction of CO₂ with primary and secondary

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram illustrating the experimental procedure employed for the thermal degradation experiments.

Fig. 3. Polarization curves of a) SS 304 L and b) SS 316 L in various APBS-CDRMax® amine solutions, at the temperature of 25 °C (L for CO₂ loaded, CONT for contaminated and CONT-L for contaminated and CO₂ loaded).

Table 2

Calculation data extracted from Tafel extrapolation for SS 304 L and 316 L: corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (I_{corr}), anodic and cathodic slopes (β_a and β_c), corrosion rates in all amine solutions tested.

	APBS-CDRMax®	E_{corr} [mV vs. SCE]	I_{corr} [μ A/cm ²]	β_c [mV/decades]	β_a [mV/decades]	Corrosion rate [μ mpy]
SS 304 L	unload	-748.2	0.1	-23.6	117.4	1.2
	load	-641	0.78	-114.7	146.6	9.2
	SO _x /NO _x unload	-698.8	0.51	-61	136.5	6
SS 316 L	SO _x /NO _x load	-641	0.76	-116.3	170.2	9.1
	unload	-656.8	0.1	-82.8	111.2	1.1
	load	-566.3	0.8	-141.1	129.6	9.2
	SO _x /NO _x unload	-687.8	0.6	-65.5	153	7
	SO _x /NO _x load	-634.9	0.7	-120.3	204.2	7.7

Fig. 4. Corrosion rates for a) SS 304 L and b) SS 316 L at 25 °C, when immersed in various APBS-CDRMax® and MEA solutions.

alkanolamines, like MEA and DEA, includes three main reactions: the carbamate formation Eq. (4), the bicarbonate formation Eq. (5) and the carbamate hydrolysis Eq. (6). Tertiary amines follow a different reaction path, forming an unstable carbamate whose break down leads to formation of bicarbonate ions Eq. (7). The existence of acid gases (like SO₂, NO, NO₂) in the flue gas result in the formation of strong acids, which can react with amines (weak bases) as in Eq. (8). The dissolution of SO₂ leads to the formation of SO₃²⁻, according to Eqs. (9), (10) [33]. When O₂ is also present in the flue gas and dissolves in the amine solvent, SO₃²⁻ are oxidized to SO₄²⁻ through a reaction that is catalyzed by dissolved Fe, Cu and Cr ions, which accumulate in the solvent due to the corrosion of equipment [34]. The dissolved SO₂ has multiple effects on solvent performance. It affects oxidative and thermal degradation reactions, but also reacts with the dissolved amine according to Eq. (8),

which in this case is written with Eqs. (11), (12) [34–36]:

Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) contained in the flue gas dissolve in an aqueous amine solution forming nitrous and nitric ions and hydrogen cations according to Eqs. (13)-(15) [37]. After dissolution, reactions with amine molecules are observed, according to Eqs. (16), (17).

Reactions referring to Eqs. (11)-(12) and (16)-(17) show that the dissolution of acid gases (SO₂ and NO_x) in the aqueous solution leads to the formation of acids in the liquid phase which protonate the amine, thereby reducing the pure amine available to react with CO₂.

Additional potential reactions involving SO_x and NO_x impurities have been discussed in a previous study [28]. From the reactions described above, it is clear that the presence of SO_x and NO_x impurities in the amine solvent can lead to the formation of new oxidizing species, which in turn promote the anodic dissolution of the metal substrate. These species include protonated amine molecules, H⁺ ions, SO₄²⁻ ions, and NO₃⁻ ions. Moreover, as previously noted, the presence of such impurities may influence the conditions required for passive film formation and stabilization by altering the chemical environment of the system, thereby further impacting its overall corrosion behavior.

4.2. Cyclic polarization curves

The resistance of stainless steels 304 L and 316 L to form localized corrosion in various corrosive environments can be assessed using cyclic polarization experiments. In this study, cyclic polarization experiments were conducted due to the detection of possible pitting corrosion in the polarization curve of SS 304 L, in unloaded APBS-CDRMax®. Fig. 5 depicts the cyclic curves for SS 304 L and 316 L samples immersed in various APBS-CDRMax® solutions, at the temperature of 25 °C. Table 3 lists critical electrochemical values drawn from the cyclic polarization curves.

One of the main concepts underlying this technique is that localized

Table 3

Calculation data of cyclic polarization curves for SS 304 L and 316 L: corrosion potential (E_{corr}), anodic-to-cathodic transition potential ($E_{a/c}$) and difference between anodic-to-cathodic transition potential to corrosion potential ($E_{a/c} - E_{corr}$).

	APBS-CDRMax®	E_{corr} [mV vs. SCE]	$E_{a/c}$ [mV vs. SCE]	$E_{a/c} - E_{corr}$ [mV vs. SCE]
SS 304 L	unload	-748.2	507	1255.2
	load	-641	248.7	889.7
	SO _x /NO _x	-698.8	478 (upper), 85 (lower)	1176.8 (upper), 783.8 (lower)
	SO _x /NO _x load	-641	267.8	908.8
SS 316 L	unload	-656.8	292	948.8
	load	-566.3	207	773.3
	SO _x /NO _x	-687.8	330.4	1018.2
	SO _x /NO _x load	-634.9	290.7	925.6

corrosion occurs when the current density of the anodic reverse scan is greater than that of the forward scan, at the same potential [38,39]. This happens because the environment within the pits is more aggressive [39]. As shown in Fig. 5, for both stainless steels, the current density in the reverse scan is consistently lower than in the forward scan across all examined cases, forming a negative hysteresis loop. This indicates that SS 304 L and SS 316 L are not susceptible to localized corrosion. Furthermore, it is observed that the differences between the anodic-to-cathodic transition potentials and the corrosion potentials ($E_{a/c} - E_{corr}$) for each corresponding solution are lower for SS 316 L than for SS 304 L, indicating the formation of a more stable passive film on SS 316 L. For the amine solutions, whether containing SO_x and NO_x contaminants or not, the $E_{a/c} - E_{corr}$ difference is more pronounced under unloaded conditions compared to the CO₂ loaded ones for both stainless steels, suggesting enhanced passivity and the development of a more protective oxide film in the unloaded solutions. Moreover, when comparing the $E_{a/c} - E_{corr}$ values of the contaminated solutions to those of the uncontaminated ones, it becomes evident that the presence of SO_x and NO_x pollutants promotes conditions favorable for the formation of a stable and protective passive layer on the metal surface. In the case of SS 304 L tested in APBS-CDRMax® unloaded conditions with contaminants, the reverse scan presents two anodic-to-cathodic transition potentials. These transition potentials correspond to intersection points of anodic and cathodic Evans lines. When a material undergoes passive film formation, the reverse anodic branch is shifted to lower current densities compared to the forward scan, resulting in intersection with the unchanged cathodic line at several points. This reflects the

Fig. 5. Cyclic polarization curves of a) SS 304 L and b) SS 316 L at 25 °C, when immersed in various APBS-CDRMax® solutions.

establishment of a protective passive layer and confirms the non-susceptibility of the tested material to localized corrosion [38,40].

4.3. Material exposure studies

In addition to the electrochemical techniques used to determine the instantaneous corrosion rate, long-term exposure experiments were performed by immersing 304 L and 316 L stainless steel coupons in various APBS-CDRMax® solutions. Although electrochemical methods provide valuable insights into immediate corrosion behavior, they often omit to account for the long-term dynamics of material degradation. Specifically, instantaneous corrosion rate measurements do not consider the potential formation of protective passive films, which can significantly mitigate corrosion over extended periods. Long term exposure tests provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the materials' behavior under real-world corrosive conditions. These tests enable the assessment of key factors, including the development and durability of passive films, their resistance to degradation, and the occurrence of localized corrosion when exposed to the corrosive medium. Such insights are essential for understanding the long-term performance and reliability of stainless steels in corrosive environments. Fig. 6 depicts the weight loss results obtained from the long-term exposure experiments for both SS 304 L and SS 316 L, when immersed in various APBS-CDRMax® amine solutions, at the temperature of 25°C and 90°C. In the weight-loss experiments, the maximum mass deviation was ± 0.0005 g, which resulted in negligible variations in the corresponding weight-loss percentages.

Generally, based on the long-term exposure test results, the weight loss percentages observed are consistently very low across all studied cases, suggesting that corrosion rates are minimal for both SS 304 L and SS 316 L. Even at the elevated temperature of 90°C, it is noticed that the corrosion behavior does not change significantly, as evident from the

weight loss that continues to be significantly limited. This indicates a high level of corrosion resistance in the materials when exposed to the tested conditions, supporting their suitability for environments where minimal material degradation is essential. Even after 24 days of exposure, any change in sample weight was only detectable at the third decimal point, limiting the ability to draw clear conclusions from this method only.

In Fig. 6, it is noticed that for both stainless steels, across all APBS-CDRMax® solutions, both at 25°C and 90°C, the weight loss demonstrates a small fluctuating pattern rather than a linear trend. This fluctuating behavior suggests that processes occur on the material's surface, such as the formation or the destruction of a passive film. This indicates that APBS-CDRMax® can potentially create favorable conditions for the development of a protective film. This observation is in accordance with the results obtained from the anodic slopes of the polarization curves.

It is also noteworthy that almost after 12 days of exposure for both SS 304 L and SS 316 L, the corrosion process shows a clear tendency to stabilize, across almost all tested solutions. This means that a balance has been reached between the rate of material loss and the passive film formation, which slows the degradation pace of the substrate. This equilibration could also potentially suggest the long-term stability of the APBS-CDRMax® solvent.

To improve the reliability of the results, 3–5 independent repetitions of the weight loss measurements were conducted, using separate stainless steel samples under identical test conditions. The measurements were performed with a high-precision analytical balance (± 0.1 mg resolution), and care was taken to ensure consistent cleaning, drying, and handling procedures across all samples. Additionally, the dimensions of the samples were increased to amplify the measurable effect.

To further support the validity of the data, average weight loss was calculated (shown in Fig. 6) and standard deviation (not shown in the

Fig. 6. Results from weight loss measurements of (a, b) SS 304 L at 25 °C and 90 °C and (c, d) SS 316 L at 25 °C and 90 °C, after several days of exposure in various APBS-CDRMax® amine solutions (L for CO₂ loaded, CONT for contaminated and CONT-L for contaminated and CO₂ loaded).

figure) across repetitions, which showed good reproducibility and low variability. While the absolute mass loss was indeed small, approaching the lower detection limit of gravimetric methods, the consistency across samples suggests that the weight loss measurements are representative of the material's long-term behavior in this environment.

4.4. Thermal degradation studies

Experimental results presented in this section are average values of the experimental measurements. Uncertainties stem directly from the measuring instrument or calculated by the error propagation method. Uncertainties of viscosity represent the standard deviation during the time of measurement, while uncertainties of density arise from the scale accuracy.

4.4.1. Evaluation of metal accumulation in solvent after prolonged contact

Inductively Coupled Plasma analysis is performed on both unloaded and CO₂-loaded APBS-CDRMax® and MEA solutions containing contaminants and aged under high acid concentration and temperature (3.1 wt% of total acids and 90°C) in contact with SS 316 L (Fig. 7). ICP analysis is commonly applied to monitor the course of corrosion via metal accumulation providing valuable information on the solvent's corrosivity during pilot plant operation [41,42]. In the following paragraphs, emphasis is placed primarily on the "contaminated and loaded" series, as it is most representative of real operating conditions, whereas "contaminated" APBS-CDRMax® and MEA are measured to establish a reference for each solvent and to quantify the effect of CO₂ presence.

The APBS-CDRMax® solvent exhibits overall a very low concentration of accumulated metals that do not exceed 1.1 ppm after 30 days of ageing. As expected, both in "contaminated-unloaded" and "contaminated and loaded" series Fe is found at the highest concentration, being the primary component of SS 316. In "contaminated and loaded" APBS-CDRMax®, Fe is found in the highest concentration (0.56 ppm), followed by Ni (0.267 ppm) and Cr (0.113 ppm). Mn is detected at concentrations lower than 0.100 ppm (0.018 ppm), whereas Mo is not detected at all. Especially, "contaminated and loaded" APBS-CDRMax® exhibits a noticeable trend in all cases, which is a significant reduction of metal concentration after the 20th day of ageing described by a

polynomial trendline. As a result, the metal concentration approaches values measured on the 10th day. The declining Fe concentration is attributed to the formation of a protective FeCO₃ layer that (partially but) effectively seems to inhibit corrosion. A similar trend is observed for Ni and Cr concentrations, suggesting the possible formation of oxide layers or some kind of complex deposits. Given the relatively high percentages of these elements (10 % Ni and 17.5 % Cr in SS 316 L), it is assumed that they also play a significant role in metal protection, through deposition processes. The "contaminated and loaded" series of MEA exhibits no significant variations in the concentrations of Fe, Ni and Cr. Compared to MEA, "contaminated-CO₂ loaded" APBS-CDRMax® exhibits 37.6 % lower Fe and 36.3 % lower Cr concentrations on the 30th day of ageing. Ni concentration appears 66 % higher in APBS-CDRMax®, which could not be interpreted with the available data, however still remaining at very low values, below 0.370 ppm.

Comparing the accumulation of Fe, Ni and Cr in APBS-CDRMax® and MEA, it is observed that during the first 10 days of exposure, MEA consistently exhibits quite lower concentrations of these elements in most cases. The higher elemental concentration in the APBS-CDRMax® solution suggests greater metal dissolution over time. However, this does not necessarily indicate higher corrosion, as it contrasts with the corrosion rates derived from potentiodynamic curves. It is important to note that while ICP analysis measures the total Fe accumulated in solution over time, potentiodynamic tests provide an instantaneous snapshot of electrochemical behavior. SEM analysis further clarifies this discrepancy, revealing substantial Fe-rich corrosion product deposition on samples exposed to MEA, suggesting that Fe²⁺ ions precipitate rather than remain in solution. In contrast, exposure to APBS-CDRMax® resulted in minimal iron precipitation, indicating a different dissolution mechanism where Fe ions stay predominantly soluble in the amine solution. Additionally, definitive conclusions regarding corrosion behavior cannot be drawn based solely on these comparative results, due to the absence of crucial data on the initial stages of exposure. This is also supported by the immersion results in Fig. 6, which show a weight gain up to the 10th day of exposure, followed by stabilization thereafter. A significant observation is also that in the case of "contaminated and loaded" solvents, both for APBS-CDRMax® and MEA, the elemental concentrations are higher compared to "contaminated and unloaded"

Fig. 7. a) Fe, b) Ni and c) Cr metal accumulation in contaminated-unloaded and contaminated-CO₂ loaded APBS-CDRMax® and MEA. Solvent annotation CONT is used for the "contaminated" series. CONT-L is used for "contaminated and loaded" series. Average measurement error is $\pm 5\%$.

solvents. This can be attributed to the increased cathodic reactions occurring in the presence of CO₂ [28], which induce more intense anodic reactions.

4.4.2. Evaluation of physical properties with possible links to corrosion

It is well established that amine degradation plays a significant role in the corrosion process [43,44]. To investigate whether the observed stabilization of corrosion in the immersion experiments is attributable to the stability of the solvent, APBS-CDRMax® is subjected to the ageing protocol, and its physical properties are measured and compared to those of MEA.

Thermal degradation occurs mainly at regenerator and reboiler conditions, where temperatures are high and there is extensive CO₂ flashing. Such conditions can cause amine loss by initiating a carbamate polymerization mechanism [45] and transforming the initial amine molecules to aldehydes, VOCs and other byproducts, possibly incapable of CO₂ capture. Furthermore, an effect of degradation could be the unwanted variation of physical properties, like density and viscosity.

When circulated in a capture plant, the solvent would face consecutive cycles of heating and cooling (typically absorption around 40 °C, regeneration around 120 °C). Thus, high temperatures would only be encountered for limited time periods, depending on plant dimensioning (rich-lean heat exchanger, desorber column and reboiler) and operating parameters that dictate the respective residence times. However, according to the thermal degradation - ageing protocol, APBS-CDRMax® and MEA are exposed for up to 720 h to 90 °C, hence, at quite intense conditions that could possibly lead to an overestimation of the effect of thermal degradation.

Fig. 8 presents comparative data on solvent degradation rates, Ψ . In both the contaminated-unloaded and contaminated-CO₂-loaded series, APBS-CDRMax® exhibits very little solvent loss that is constantly lower than that of MEA. The “contaminated” series of APBS-CDRMax® exhibits a marginal 1.02 % amine content loss after 30 days of ageing, whereas MEA exhibits a 3-fold loss (3.11 %). The “contaminated and loaded” series of APBS-CDRMax® exhibits 2.5 % amine loss after 30 days, whereas MEA exhibits 5.92 %. The stability of amine content in APBS-CDRMax® is in good agreement with the minor formation of degradation products and scarce observation of relative depositions on the metallic specimens that were in prolonged contact with the solvent (see Section 3.5).

The increase of a solvent’s viscosity and density is associated with the formation and accumulation of degradation products, like heat stable salts, and can be monitored as a sign of ageing/degradation [46]. Increased viscosity may affect the penetration, diffusion coefficients, and mass transfer rate of CO₂ into the amine solution and may possibly influence the efficiency of the absorption/desorption process [46]. A solvent that exhibits limited property variations is preferable as it can facilitate the operation of the absorption/desorption process.

A trend of increasing density and viscosity has indeed been reported after 1843 h of plant operation with 30 % aqueous MEA as contaminants and degradation products accumulated in the circulating solvent [46]. The experiments are conducted with a fixed initial contaminant concentration (3.1 wt% of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃), which remained constant and possibly triggered the formation of degradation species during high-temperature treatment. During the ageing protocol heat stable salt formation may have occurred as no degassing was implemented before sealing the containers, and the solvent was in contact with the atmospheric air present in them.

Both “contaminated” and “contaminated and loaded” series of APBS-CDRMax® show lower variation of viscosity, η , compared to MEA (see normalized measurements in Figs. 9a and 9b). For measurements performed at 40 °C, specifically, after 30 days of ageing APBS-CDRMax® shows 9.2 % increased viscosity under unloaded conditions and 37.4 % increase under CO₂-loaded conditions, respectively. MEA, on the contrary, exhibits significant variation of viscosity, which is an unfavorable situation with various possible implications on pilot plant operation. After 30 days, MEA exhibits 102 % increased viscosity under unloaded conditions and 77.8 % increased viscosity under CO₂-loaded conditions, respectively. This is over two times higher variation, underlining that APBS-CDRMax® is of superior stability. The same trends appear when measurements are performed at 60 °C, where APBS-CDRMax® and MEA appear with a 37.6 % and 81.8 % increased viscosity respectively.

Similarly, stable behavior is revealed after measuring density, ρ , of APBS-CDRMax® series at room temperature (Fig. 9c). After 30 days, the unloaded series show a small increase of density, reaching 1 % for APBS-CDRMax® and 3 % for MEA. The “contaminated and loaded” APBS-CDRMax® exhibits a mere 0.1 % decrease in density, whereas MEA exhibits 0.58 %. The lowering of density could be due to some desorption of CO₂ from the liquid phase after prolonged treatment at 90 °C. Anyhow, the difference is marginal, and the solvent’s density may be considered unaltered.

4.5. Scanning electron microscopy analysis

The characterization of the specimens after polarization corrosion tests in various APBS-CDRMax® amine solutions at 25 °C is shown in Figs. 10 and 11. These images can provide valuable information regarding the distribution, quantity and size of the deposits that have been formed on the corroded surfaces. Overall, the microstructural characteristics of both stainless steels are similar, though the extent of corrosion products appears slightly more pronounced on the surface of SS 316 L.

Fig. 10 illustrates the microstructure of specimens immersed in both unloaded and loaded conditions, without SO_x/NO_x contaminants, for SS 304 L and SS 316 L. SEM images reveal minimal material degradation, as the corroded substrate closely resembles the non-corroded one,

Fig. 8. Degradation rate occurring due to thermal treatment causing amine content loss for a) “Contaminated” series and b) “Contaminated and loaded” series of APBS-CDRMax® and MEA. The solvents were aged at 90 °C for up to 30 days.

Fig. 9. Percentage change compared to initial values of a) Viscosity measured at 40°C, b) Viscosity measured at 60°C and c) Density measured at 25°C for “contaminated”, “contaminated and loaded” series of APBS-CDRMax[®] and MEA. The solvents were aged for up to 30 days at 90°C.

Fig. 10. Microstructural characteristics of: [a, b] SS 304 L immersed in unloaded and loaded APBS-CDRMax[®] and [c, d] SS 316 L immersed in unloaded and loaded APBS-CDRMax[®] amine solutions.

indicating a very low corrosion rate. Additionally, the SEM images show the presence of small, of irregular and non-uniform morphology corrosion products on the surfaces of the corroded specimens, which may act as protective layers. A few black areas are also visible on the metal surface, primarily composed of Fe, C, and N, as identified through EDX analysis. These regions are associated with by-products formed from the decomposition of the amine solution. Notably, the limited presence of these black areas confirms the high stability of APBS-CDRMax[®] solvent degradation.

Fig. 11 depicts the microstructure of specimens exposed to amine

Fig. 11. Microstructural characteristics of: [a, b] SS 304 L immersed in unloaded and loaded APBS-CDRMax[®] and [c, d] SS 316 L immersed in unloaded and loaded APBS-CDRMax[®] amine solutions.

solutions containing SO_x/NO_x contaminants. In these cases, the metal substrate is coated with black layers of varying thickness, which are significantly more pronounced compared to the solutions without contaminants. Corrosion products resembling those found in APBS-CDRMax[®] unloaded and loaded solutions were also present. Notably, the surface of SS 316 L is partially covered by a variety of morphologies, including cross-shaped, leaf-like, and needle-like structures. These corrosion products probably act as protective layers that inhibit the overall corrosion process and are likely attributed to reactions occurring with the buffer salts contained in the amine solution, as mentioned in the

introduction. In general, the presence of corrosion precipitations on the metal surface is in accordance with the results of polarization curves, which suggest the formation of passive film, due to its low coverage, the film is not truly protective, as also indicated by the pseudo-passive region in the polarization curves.

Even after an immersion period of 30 days in APBS-CDRMax® at 90°C, the SS 316 L specimens present the same type of corrosion products, as those detected after the polarization experiments. Consequently, we can generally categorize the formation of three kinds of degradation products. Namely, i) depositions with crystal-like morphology, ii) darker spots containing carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O), iii) other depositions containing Fe, Cr, Ni, silicon (Si), which may exhibit a dark gray layer on top. The products under the first category are shown in Fig. 12a. Their formation is attributed to the presence of buffer salts. For the products of category (ii) (Fig. 12a) the atomic analysis suggests that they must be an organic chemical compound, given the strong presence of C and N, likely indicating an amine degradation product adhering to the metal surface. It should be mentioned that, although EDX analysis does not accurately detect elements such as carbon, oxygen and nitrogen, the significantly high percentages reported for these elements clearly confirm their presence (Table 4). However, the reported concentrations may not precisely reflect their true quantities. Products of category (iii) (Fig. 12b) contain components with ratios quite close to SS 316 L material. This could indicate that the deposited material is very thin and the EDX beam penetrates it, thus only detecting the metal substrate. The same examination was also conducted on the corresponding SS304L specimens. The EDX analyses yielded results essentially identical to those obtained for SS316L, indicating that the formation and composition of the corrosion-inhibiting products are comparable in both alloys. For the sake of clarity and to avoid redundancy, only the SS316L data are presented in the manuscript, as they are fully representative of the behavior of SS304L under the same experimental conditions.

5. Conclusions

The present study examines the corrosion behavior of two stainless steels (304 L and 316 L) when exposed to APBS-CDRMax®, either without CO₂ or loaded with CO₂, both with and without the presence of acidic contaminants, at the temperature of 25°C and 90°C. Solvent stability assessment is also included in this study, based on a solvent ageing protocol coupled with physical property and metal accumulation measurements, providing comparative results with the baseline solvent MEA 30 %. The key findings are summarized as follows:

The corrosion rates in APBS-CDRMax® are exceptionally low (<10 µm/Y), despite the solvent being loaded with CO₂. The corrosion rates are significantly lower than those observed for the benchmark MEA solvent.

The corrosion rate of the APBS-CDRMax® exhibits only a marginal change upon the addition of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ acids to the solvent.

APBS-CDRMax® demonstrated it can provide the conditions required for passivation over a wide range of voltages.

No pitting corrosion is observed in any of the examined solutions, for both SS 304 L and SS 316 L.

Microstructural analysis reveals the formation of deposited compounds possibly stemming from the inherent nature of APBS-CDRMax®. This is particularly pronounced in solutions containing H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ contaminants, with a more intense accumulation on the surface of SS 316 L.

Long term exposure tests indicate a tendency for protective layer formation in APBS-CDRMax® and confirm the extremely low corrosivity of this solvent.

Under this ageing protocol, APBS-CDRMax® exhibits signs of very limited degradation. In all cases, viscosity variations are significantly lower compared to that of MEA, whereas density shows practically no variation. Metal accumulation measurements reveal a passivation

Fig. 12. SEM images of degradation products deposited on SS 316 specimen's surface and results of EDX analysis, after 30 days of immersion at 90 °C: [a] category (ii) product and [b] category (iii) product.

Table 4

Summary table presenting the elemental percentages of the corrosion degradation products presented in Fig. 12.

category (ii)		category (iii)	
weight	conc (%)	weight	conc (%)
C	43.24	Fe	64.50
O	21.08	Cr	16.45
N	20.06	Ni	12.84
Fe	5.72	Mo	3.74
Mo	2.06	Mn	1.68
other elements	Bal.	Si	0.79

behavior, in accordance with observations from electrochemical techniques and long-term exposure tests, leading to very low concentrations of metals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Evie Nessi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Fani Stergioudi:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Eleni Lamprou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **James Hall:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Papadopoulos Athanasios:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Panagiotis Seferlis:** Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Nikolaos Michailidis:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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